

SOME CHALLENGES TO TEACH WRITING TO A2 LEVEL LEARNERS.

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Annotation: Common challenge faced by A2 level learners in their writing is the limited vocabulary and grammatical accuracy, which can hinder their ability to express themselves fluently and effectively. A2 level learners may encounter difficulties in using appropriate vocabulary and grammatical structures, resulting in simplistic and repetitive writing. In this article, we focus on this challenges.

When asked to describe a memorable event, A2 level learners may struggle to find the right words to convey their experiences vividly. Their writing may lack variety and precision, as they rely on a limited range of vocabulary. As Murray and Christison point out, "A2 level learners often have a restricted repertoire of vocabulary, which can restrict the depth and complexity of their compositions."

Similarly, A2 level learners may face challenges in applying grammatical structures accurately, leading to errors and inaccuracies in their writing. They may struggle with verb tenses, subject-verb agreement, word order, and other grammatical aspects, impacting the clarity and coherence of their compositions. Hedge (2015) emphasizes that "A2 level learners may make errors in basic grammatical structures, which can affect the overall quality of their writing."

To address this problem, educators can implement strategies to enhance vocabulary and grammatical accuracy in A2 level learners' writing. One approach is providing explicit instruction on target vocabulary related to specific writing tasks. By introducing new words, phrases, and expressions and encouraging their use in writing, learners can expand their vocabulary repertoire and convey their ideas more precisely. Engaging A2 level learners in regular reading activities can expose them to a wider range of vocabulary and grammatical structures. By exploring authentic texts, learners can observe how words are used in context and how grammatical forms are employed, thus

enhancing their understanding and application of vocabulary and grammar in their own writing.

In addition, incorporating targeted grammar exercises and activities into writing lessons can help address grammatical challenges. By focusing on specific grammar points and providing practice opportunities, educators can assist A2 level learners in improving their grammatical accuracy and reducing errors in their writing. Providing constructive feedback and error correction plays a crucial role in supporting A2 level learners' vocabulary and grammatical development. By highlighting errors and offering explanations or alternative expressions, educators can help learners identify and rectify their mistakes, promoting increased accuracy in their writing.

In conclusion, the limited vocabulary and grammatical accuracy pose significant challenges for A2 level learners in their writing proficiency. By incorporating strategies such as explicit vocabulary instruction, extensive reading, targeted grammar activities, and effective feedback, educators can support A2 level learners in expanding their vocabulary repertoire, improving grammatical accuracy, and enhancing the fluency and effectiveness of their writing.

Another significant challenge faced by A2 level learners in their writing development is the struggle with the development of critical thinking and analytical skills, which are crucial for organizing ideas and presenting coherent arguments. A2 level learners often find it challenging to generate and develop ideas beyond surface-level descriptions, resulting in compositions that lack depth and complexity.

For instance, when tasked with writing an argumentative essay on a social issue, A2 level learners may struggle to provide logical reasoning and evidence to support their stance. Their writing may be limited to stating opinions without substantial supporting information or fail to present a well-structured argument. As Williams highlights, "A2 level learners may struggle to think critically and analyze information to construct well-developed arguments."

Additionally, A2 level learners may face difficulties in organizing their thoughts in a systematic and coherent manner. They may struggle to connect ideas logically and present them in a cohesive and persuasive manner. Their writing may lack a clear introduction, body paragraphs with supporting evidence, and a concise conclusion. Hedge states that "A2 level learners may find it challenging to structure their writing in a coherent and organized manner to effectively communicate their ideas." To address this challenge, educators can implement strategies that promote critical thinking and analytical skills in A2 level learners'

writing. One effective approach is to provide explicit instruction on the elements of argumentation, such as stating a clear claim, providing supporting evidence, and addressing counterarguments. By guiding learners through the process of developing well-structured arguments, educators can help A2 level learners improve their critical thinking abilities (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2000).

Moreover, engaging learners in activities that require analysis and evaluation can enhance their critical thinking skills. For example, educators can provide A2 level learners with texts or prompts that require them to analyze different perspectives or evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of various arguments. By guiding learners through these activities, educators can foster their ability to think critically and develop more sophisticated arguments (Hinkel, 2015). Encouraging A2 level learners to engage in reflective writing can support the development of analytical skills. By asking learners to reflect on their own thinking process, evaluate the effectiveness of their arguments, and suggest improvements, educators can promote self-awareness and metacognitive skills that contribute to better organization and coherence in their writing (Johns & Price, 2016).

Furthermore, providing A2 level learners with models of well-structured and coherent writing can serve as a reference point for their own development. By analyzing and deconstructing sample essays or paragraphs, learners can gain insights into the organization of ideas, the use of supporting evidence, and the overall coherence of effective writing (Raimes, 1983). The development of critical thinking and analytical skills presents a significant challenge for A2 level learners in their writing proficiency. By implementing strategies such as explicit instruction on argumentation, engaging in analysis and evaluation activities, promoting reflective writing, and providing models of effective writing, educators can support A2 level learners in enhancing their critical thinking abilities and organizing their ideas coherently.

All in all, teaching writing to A2 level learners requires a deep understanding of their specific challenges and needs. By addressing the issues related to paragraph organization, vocabulary usage, and critical thinking skills, educators can effectively support A2 level learners in their writing development.

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